

	<p>OR XB (YouTube) OR XB (Instagram) OR XB (Tiktok) OR XB (Whatsapp) OR XB (WeChat) OR XB (Telegram) OR XB (Snapchat) OR XB (Douyin) OR XB (BeReal) OR XB (Reddit) OR XB (Discord)</p> <p>Filters: 01/01/1990 - 12/31/2025; Randomized Controlled Trials; English</p>	
PsycInfo	<p>XB (Type 1 diabetes) OR XB (T1D) OR MM (Diabetes Mellitus, Type 1)</p> <p>AND</p> <p>XB (artificial intelligence) OR XB (AI) OR XB (machine learning) OR XB (deep learning) OR XB (natural language processing) OR XB (neural networks) OR XB (sentiment analysis) OR XB (LLM) OR XB (Large Language Model*) OR XB (Chatbot) OR XB (mhealth) OR XB (mobile health) OR XB (mobile app) OR XB (mobile application*) OR XB (app) OR XB (digital health) OR XB (connected health) OR XB (smartwatch) OR XB (wearable) OR XB (sensor) OR XB (smartphone) OR XB (ehealth) OR XB (e-health) OR XB (website) OR XB (web portal) OR XB (Internet) OR XB (social network*) OR XB (social media) OR XB (online community) OR XB (Facebook) OR XB (Twitter) OR XB (X) OR XB (YouTube) OR XB (Instagram) OR XB (Tiktok) OR XB (Whatsapp) OR XB (WeChat) OR XB (Telegram) OR XB (Snapchat) OR XB (Douyin) OR XB (BeReal) OR XB (Reddit) OR XB (Discord)</p> <p>Filters: 1990-2025; Clinical Trial; English</p>	8
Clinicaltrials.gov	<p>"Type 1 diabetes" OR "T1D" OR "Diabetes Mellitus, Type 1" Other terms: "artificial intelligence" OR "AI" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "natural language processing" OR "neural networks" OR "sentiment analysis" OR "LLM" OR "Large Language Model*" OR "Chatbot" OR "mhealth" OR "mobile health" OR "mobile app" OR "mobile application*" OR "app" OR "digital health" OR "connected health" OR "smartwatch" OR "wearable" OR "sensor" OR "smartphone" OR "ehealth" OR "e-health" OR "website" OR "web portal" OR "Internet" OR "social network*" OR "social media" OR "online community" OR "Facebook" OR "Twitter" OR "X" OR "YouTube" OR "Instagram" OR "Tiktok" OR "Whatsapp" OR "WeChat" OR "Telegram" OR "Snapchat" OR "Douyin" OR "BeReal" OR "Reddit" OR "Discord"</p> <p>Filters: 1990-2025 (Study start);</p>	958

Search date: 11/09/2025